

Customer Service (Using Bot's) and Consumer Relations- A Tool for Sustainable Business Development

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Abstract

The purpose of the paper is to demonstrate customer service and consumer relations is a key for sustainable business development. This study explores how organization approach customer service and consumer relation towards its success. The study also provides further insight into the mediating effect by considering and assessing various service tools identification for its success. The rationale behind this study is to address major gaps in the customer service in India, where the major focus has been on the side of production and sales.

Design/ Methodology Approach

This research begins by developing a framework to address the customer service and also to examine the relationship between it and sustainable business development. Second to check, whether there a positive and significant effect on the sustainable development based on customer service and retention through secondary data study. This study is mainly exploratory and casual in nature.

Introduction

Customer service is an important criterion for the company to be in the business for the longer period of time. When I say longer period it is for their sustainability. Companies these days have to really show more focus towards customer service. These days consumers want the product/service manufacturers to be with them till product/service becomes obsolete. Even after there the next important thing is being how to retain the customer with this. As everyone know consumer acquisition is much costly than before as more and more companies differentiate their offering at least on a yearly basis, which means in a year if 12 months each and every month there is a change and customers will loose their on the focus on differentiation easily.

Customer service not only applies to physical products but it also applies to service sector, in fact the number of enquiries are more in

service sectors like (Banking and Finance). Hence it is high time that for every business sustainability the need for the hour is customer service as a result of which there will be reciprocation of what we call as customer retention. On the other hand there has been a lot of improvements in data sciences especially AI, Now even Harvard Business Review says that the next most admired job would be data science and Artificial Intelligence. But is there a correlation between AI and customer service, my answer would be yes as AI has been used or being used as a replacement in the name of bots by most companies. Hence my topic basically revolves around the usage of BOTS in the customer service and thereby increasing the customer retention.

We also see there has been a lot of interface been seen in mobile phones these days which takes the command for their users to do the most routine and mundane works in the job.

Literature Review

By Paul Korzeniowski

Science fiction has long promoted intelligent computer systems, either empowering humans, like Data in Star Trek: The Next Generation, or terrorizing them, like HAL in 2001: A Space Odyssey. While current systems have not yet reached the level of sophistication where they act like humans. The usage of bots in customer care has gained momentum, as consumers continue to demand faster and better service. With more companies adopting bots in their customer care strategies to solve for this demand, Live Person commissioned a survey of 5,000 global consumers to uncover consumer attitudes toward bots in customer care. Robotic Process Automation (RPA) tools are a critical emerging technology for customer service professionals trying to enhance customer experiences and increase customer service efficiencies in 2019.

Customerserviceacross the World Using Bots

According to Grand View Research, AI Chabot market size is estimated to hit \$1.25 Billion by 2025. It has also been predicted that 30% of the online searches will be through voice directions.

In a recent survey, reports revealed that 64% of people said 24-hour service of best AI Chabot is a huge benefit of their business. Yes it has been estimated that more than 67% if the customer service has been done using Chabotin India. It is also been predicted that 85% of the human interactions will be handled by the BOT. Yes in most of the countries consumers accept the role of chat bots in their conversation, but there are countries where they don't even like to interact with the Chabot's.

Countries like Germany they show more apprehension towards chat bots and they have even named them as "Killer Bots" or some even say they are "Job Stealers". Most successful companies Bots are IBM's Watson. In fact this BOT defeats two human champions who are good in handling customers before national television audience, There has been a tremendous impact of AI's in Chabot's and global companies like IBM are very successful in implementing it. Similarly companies like Microsoft which introduced it BOT in the year 1995 was considered to be milestone but compared to that we now have come up a very long way from BOB.

But then the question arises whether Chabot have been accepted by the customers. To a certain extent customer would be able to receive a message at least from the company's side that by itself helps the customer to think positive about the company. But in spite of repeated reminders by the customer side when there is no effect on service, there arises the problem. One of the recent study found the below mentioned facts.

- 1) 57% of UK consumers know what a Chabot is.
- 2) 55% of consumers are interested in interacting with a business using messaging apps to solve a problem.
- 3) 57% of consumers are interested in Chabot's for their instantaneity.

- 4) 15% of US consumers believe nothing could stop them from using a Chabot. (Convince and convert, 2018).
- 5) 48% of consumers prefer a Chabot that solves issues over a Chabot that has personality. (Business Insider, 2017).
- 6) 7% of US adults would buy basic items through a Chabot. (Drift, 2018)

Bots Usage in India

The usage of Bots started in the year 2015, it has been predicted that BOTS usage has been growing at the rate of 35% CAGR. Nevertheless India has been the late adopter of this advanced tech, but now it is the key player in chat bot market. Indian customers are looking more for the outcomes through digital assistants. There has been a lot of industries which have got a sizable amount of BOT usage in customer service. The major industry which is taking the lead is Banking and Insurance.

In India there has been an enormous amount of research being done in developing new BOTS. It has been found that in India more than 100 Chabot startups have been involved in developing BOTS for customer service. At present India lies in the second position in using Chatbots next to USA. The percentage of chat bots used at present is 11 % which is next to USA which stands at 36% in customer service.

(Source: Statistacequity Analysis)

This has been largely possible because of the huge internet subscribers. According to the recent study it has been found that India has more than 250 Million internet users till 2018, and it has been estimated that it will grow to the level of 291 million users before 2019, this mainly propelled by the huge amount of rural consumers joining the internet bandwagon.

Companies which Use Bots in India

EVA: This Bot has been used by HDFC based on Artificial Intelligence (AI platform), which handles 85% of the customer enquiries in banking and insurance sector. Have answered at least 5 mn queries so far from one million customers.

LAWBOT: Basically analyze and reviews legal documents. Helps to collect and organize statutes and case histories relevant to the case search.

TIA: A personal Loan assistant of TATA Group. 25% of Tata capital utilizes BOT for loan assistance.

CARA: BOT utilized by TCS which handles general Enquires and also the queries related to HR policy to the employees, Milo Chabot also is used to facilitate the Mentoring Process in TCS.

IGNIO: used by Tata steel for faster decision making, currently 83% of the request and also for its subsidiary are handled by the BOT.

These are some of the examples, but there are more and more companies now are on the verge of using BOTS to handle their customer service effectively.

Advantages of Using Bots

- 1) **Reduced cost:** The labor cost and the hiring cost will come down and also the cost of implantation of BOT technology has been reduced drastically for 2015 onwards.
- 2) **24/7 availability:** Customers don't have to wait till the executive come, and more over the customers are taken care when the traffics are high.
- 3) **Learning and updating:** When BOTS interact they learn on their own, based on their learning they update on their own.
- 4) **Multiple customers handling:** Handle many queries as required and there is a possibility that no customer stays un attended.
- 5) **Update new Technology:** The technology has been updated then and there itself as the Machine learning concept has been growing farther and further. Moreover the updation of the technology is much faster when it comes to BOTs.
- 6) **Implementation of Newer service:** Yes new services can be added to it much faster it basically addition/ updation to the existing product.

Disadvantages of Using Bots

- 1) **Complex Interface:** Lots of time is required to have more and more interface. Similarly if the need of the customer requirement increases the interface may become more complex in nature.
- 2) **Inability to understand:** There are two types of BOTS. If the bot is a fixed program in nature then bots may not be able to answer to all the queries.
- 3) **High Cost:** Sometimes when we completely rely only on Bots, there is a possibility that the cost of the installation might shoot up.
- 4) **Zero Decision Making:** Bots can only encourage giving an answer but they are unable to make real decision as such.
- 5) **Poor Memory:** The memory has to continuously update as bots have to access the customer's earlier queries.

Customer Retention

Lot of factors plays an important role to retain the customer. But to retain a customer the main factor is the kind of service offered before and after sales. As everyone accepts the fact of the matter that acquiring a new customer is expensive, so by retaining the customer company would save costs. There has been a lot of qualitative and quantitative measurement which predicts that BOTS are used well in the organization and one such measurement is customer retention.

Conclusion

From the above secondary data analysis, it has been found that there has been a significant amount of work is being done on the research as well as the usage pattern of BOTS in the customer service. Lot of research which has been done earlier also proves that at least to 25% of the customer queries have been handled effectively in managing the customers. This has ultimately reduced the cost of running the call center operations as well as retaining the customer service to the maximum extent. The scope of this research also falls in finding out the different BOTS used by the companies and the percentage of services which are completed through bots. In India , even though we usage BOTS but still we are in the nascent stage of development in using the same, but surely there is a time but not very far, that we surely will see a area change in using the bots for customer service and retaining customers.

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